
Exploring Horizons: Publish with us to Impact Surgery

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Impact Surgery aims to expand options for authors of surgical research, with a fast, flexible platform that can offer deep dives on a wide range of surgical topics. It aims to be cross-cutting across all surgical and perioperative disciplines, appealing to the generality of surgery. Our goal is to be inclusive of ethnicity, gender, income status, and other markers of diversity.

We aspire to be globally representative, actively seeking research contributions from across the Global South. We aim to publish Editorials, Reviews, Original Research, Abstracts and Education articles that are methodologically sound, irrespective of conclusion. In doing so, we aim to offer rapid peer review by a team of trained reviewers, who focus on reporting and methodology, rather than forcing unnecessarily long peer reviews.

As a fully open-access, independent initiative, we strive to provide value for money and contribute to the fair redistribution of the financial ecosystem by supporting academics involved in the review process.

Our overarching ambition is to establish a series of flexible journals under the umbrella of the Impact Health Publishing Group. Following Impact Surgery, our next ventures include Impact Health, a general medical journal, and Impact Quality Improvement, which concentrates on reporting quality improvement studies. Recognizing the inherent risks, we embark on a one-year pilot of Impact Surgery with the determination to succeed in this high-risk venture.

We eagerly anticipate engaging with potential authors, embracing a wide array of studies from various disciplines. We invite and encourage innovative ideas to foster community engagement and look forward to the ongoing dialogue with our community.